

IPBES Data Management Tutorials

Chapter 2: IPBES data management policy

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4014790](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4014790)

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Description of Chapter

The chapter provides an introduction of the IPBES data and knowledge management policy. It discusses why IPBES has a data and knowledge management policy and who is responsible for the implementation and further development of this policy.

Please note that the IPBES data and knowledge management policy is the second version of the IPBES data management policy.

Overview of Sessions:

- *Session 2.1: Introduction to the data management policy*
 - Defines what a data management policy is and why it is important.
 - DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4018580](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4018580)
- *Session 2.2: Why IPBES has a data management policy and how it concerns experts*
 - Provides background on what IPBES wants to achieve with its data management policy and how it impacts experts within IPBES. The session now has a supplement which covers the development of the policy from version 1.0 to 2.0.
 - DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4014818](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4014818)
- *Session 2.3: Roles and responsibilities*
 - Outlines the responsibilities of all involved players as stipulated in the IPBES Data Management Policy. These are discussed in light of the importance for IPBES experts.
 - DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4014820](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4014820)
- *Session 2.4: Implementation of the data management policy*
 - Provides a brief overview of the contents of the following chapters and how it all works together to improve the transparency and credibility of IPBES.
 - DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4018587](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4018587)

Suggested citation:

Krug, R. M., Addink, W., Nelson, H. P. (2022) Chapter 2: IPBES data management policy, in Krug, R. M., Aboki Omare, B. D., Niamir (eds.) IPBES Data Management Tutorials, IPBES Task Force on Knowledge and Data. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4014790](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4014790)

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